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Self-healing Properties of Carbon-black Impregnated Thermoplastic Polyurethane Processed via Fused Deposition Modelling

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Overview

- Self-healing polymers can recover damages such as fractures, corruptions, scratches,...
- Carbon-Black as a material that absorbs microwave, added to Thermoplastic Polyurethane (TPU) which is transparent to microwave.
- Self-healing properties of the created material was investigated.

Material Preparation

Thermoplastic Polyurethane
(TPU) in pellet form

Carbon-Black

Crushed into TPU powder

Mixture of
TPU- CB (5 wt%)

Extrusion

3D-Printing Filament
for Fused Deposition Modelling
(FDM)

Sample Preparation

Preparation of G-Code file for 3D-printing

3D-Printing using pure TPU

3D-Printing using TPU-CB

Creating damage in some of the samples

Cutting depth = 0.8mm

Top view

2 mm

0.8mm

Side view

Experiments

- Tensile test (ASTM D412) applied on different series of 3D printed samples including:
 - A. 3D-Printed TPU material-Not damaged
 - B. 3D-Printed TPU-CB material- Not damaged
 - C. 3D-Printed TPU-CB material- Damaged
 - D. 3D-Printed TPU-CB material- Damaged and then Healed

- Healing efficiency was measured based on the tensile strength of the healed and virgin samples.

$$\eta = \frac{\textit{Tensile Strength}_{\textit{Healed}} - \textit{Tensile Strength}_{\textit{Damaged}}}{\textit{Tensile Strength}_{\textit{Virgin}} - \textit{Tensile Strength}_{\textit{Damaged}}}$$

Results and Conclusion

- Presence of **CB** particles in **TPU** enables absorbing microwave
- Mechanical properties of TPU enhanced by adding CB
- Samples were able to heal in less that 20s while the microwave was aimed to the damaged area
- Healing efficiency was calculated to be 32%

Thank you

Any Questions?